

Defining the Role of Living Labs to Clinical Research: Initial Findings for Framework Development

Authors

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Abstract

Integrating research into clinical environments is critical for advancing healthcare, yet various barriers hinder healthcare professionals from participating in externally initiated research efforts. This study investigates how Living Labs can support the integration of such research into routine clinical practice. Through a mixed-methods questionnaire distributed to Living Lab practitioners, we identify key barriers including time constraints, misalignment between research agendas and clinical needs, and inadequate incentive structures. The qualitative data about Living Lab offering were thematically analysed and mapped across four research phases, planning, preparation, implementation, and dissemination, as defined by the Living Lab Management System. Preliminary results, based on responses from seven Living Labs, suggest that Living Labs can enhance research relevance, foster co-ownership among professionals, and serve as hubs for multi-stakeholder engagement. They also provide mechanisms for academic recognition and professional development, which may act as incentives for clinician participation. The outcome of this work is an initial evidence-informed framework that outlines actionable strategies to address common barriers to clinical research implementation.

Key words

Clinical environments, framework, innovation, healthcare professionals, implementation

Introduction

Integrating research into clinical environments is essential for driving innovation and improving healthcare delivery. However, healthcare professionals often face significant challenges when engaging with research activities (Aljezawi et al., 2019; Bonfim et al., 2023). These barriers are particularly evident when research is introduced by entities that operate outside traditional clinical infrastructures like companies or external researchers. Unlike internal research units embedded within healthcare organizations, these external entities might have conflicting priorities or research agendas (McDaniel et al., 2025; Wegner et al., 2022).

Living Labs, as open innovation ecosystems that promote user-centered, co-creative, and real-world experimentation, offer a promising pathway to bridge the gap between research and clinical practice. However, despite their growing presence, a structured understanding of how Living Labs can effectively support research in clinical settings remains underdeveloped. Through this lens, the study explores how the Living Lab approach can support the transition from research to implementation, ensuring that research findings are not only generated but also translated into meaningful improvements in clinical practice.

Starting with the barriers that healthcare professionals encounter when collaborating with such externally initiated research efforts, we try to identify what Living Labs can offer to address these issues. Through a mixed-methods approach, by combining rating scales and qualitative inputs from Living Lab practitioners, we introduce the first version of an evidence-informed framework aligned with the Living Lab Management System. The framework serves as a guide for facilitating smoother research integration in clinical settings. It highlights actionable strategies that leverage the strengths of LLs to enhance research relevance, feasibility, and uptake in real-world care environments.

Methodology

To examine these dynamics, a mixed-methods questionnaire was designed and distributed to Living Lab professionals with experience or exposure to research projects performed in clinical environments. The questionnaire sought to identify key barriers and assess perceptions regarding the potential of the Living Lab model in addressing them. The questionnaire was distributed through the ENoLL Health and Wellbeing Working Group communication channels.

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

Participants were first asked to rate their level of agreement with barrier-related statements using a 5-point Likert scale (1 indicating "strongly disagree" and 5 indicating "strongly agree," with an option for "not applicable"). This was followed by a second question asking the extent to which they believed that Living Labs could help address each specific barrier, again rated on a 5-point scale (from 1, "not at all," to 5, "to a great extent").

In addition to the scaled questions, respondents were invited to provide open-ended responses in three areas. They were asked to describe, in their own words, how they believed Living Labs could help address the identified challenges. They were also asked to share specific situations in which they encountered the barrier in a clinical setting, and to reflect on how, if at all, they had applied the Living Lab approach to overcome the challenge.

Barriers explored through this process emerged from both literature and stakeholder consultations (Petsani et al., 2025), and were categorized into two levels: those related to individual healthcare professionals, and those embedded in the broader care setting. The professional-level barriers included time constraints and care-flow priorities, lack of training and skills in research, misaligned incentives, limited research culture, disconnections between external research agendas and clinical priorities, and fears of negative impact on patient care. Meanwhile, care-setting barriers included internal institutional hurdles, such as complex administrative procedures and ethics approvals, external regulatory complexities, and limited cross-disciplinary collaboration within healthcare institutions.

As an initial step in analysing the collected responses, we focused on questionnaire items that received an average score above 4 on both dimensions: the level of agreement with the identified barrier and the perceived extent to which Living Labs could help address it. This prioritization allowed us to concentrate on the most pressing and widely recognized challenges for the preliminary development of the framework. Given that the framework is envisioned as an evolving tool, this phase represents an early iteration that will be refined through subsequent cycles of feedback and data collection.

The overall structure of the framework was guided by the Living Lab Research process as defined in the current version of the Living Lab Management System (Konstantinidis et al., 2024). To align the qualitative data with this structure, all open-ended responses from the questionnaire were categorized according to the research process stage they referenced. Following this classification, a thematic analysis was conducted in

accordance with the approach outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006)(Braun & Clarke, 2006), allowing for the identification of recurring patterns and themes within each stage.

Results

We have collected 7 responses from 7 different Living Labs (5 ENoLL members and 2 non-members). The categories with average rating higher than 4 was ‘Time Constraints’ and ‘Care-Flow Priorities’ (4.43 agreement and 4.14 Living Labs can address it), ‘Incentive Structures’ (4.14 agreement and 4 Living Labs can address it) and ‘Misalignment Between Research Agendas and Clinical Needs’ (4.29 agreement and 4.14 Living Labs can address it). Below, we summarize the qualitative findings and recommendations for each step of the Living Lab Research process:

1. **Planning Phase:** The planning phase, focused on identifying research needs and formulating questions, was linked to the barriers of misalignment between research agendas and clinical needs and care-flow priorities.

Two key themes emerged:

- **Prioritization and Alignment:** Participants highlighted the need to align research with clinical priorities, suggesting LLs can support this by “selecting the adequate projects” and by “designing activity lines based on system priorities set by professionals.”
 - **Professionals as Co-Creators:** Responses emphasized involving healthcare professionals early in the process, enabling them to “own the research process from inception” and fostering a “better understanding of their mutual contexts.”
2. **Preparation phase:** The preparation phase that includes resources management (e.g., funding, equipment, personnel) was linked with the barrier of ‘Time constraint’ and also the lack of ‘incentive structures’.

Three key themes emerged:

- **Academic acknowledgement:** Participants proposed that professionals should receive academic recognition, such as being “invited to be co-authors,” obtaining “certificates and co-authorship opportunities,” or receiving “participation certificates with academic value.”
- **Training opportunities:** Living Labs were seen as offering “continuous training” and “career benefits,” with “mentoring and peer support to enhance skills.”
- **Methods and tools:** “Flexible participation options” and “co-design toolkits” were highlighted as practical enablers for engagement during this phase.

3. **Implementation phase:** The implementation phase, which includes data collection, interpretation, and the development of the research report, was associated with the most prominent barriers identified: ‘time constraints’ and ‘care-flow priorities’, ‘incentive structures’, and ‘misalignment between research agendas and clinical needs’.

Two key themes emerged:

- **Real-world relevance:** Participants emphasized that Living Labs should support “research directly relevant to their clinical practice,” promote “real-world validation,” and ensure “not testing but real implementation.” One noted that LLs can embed research “in a way that [it] is an effortless by-product” of care delivery.
- **Hub of multistakeholder engagement:** LLs were described as “serving as a hub for innovations” and “mediating between laboratories and healthcare professionals.” This positioning enables LLs to “serve as hubs of practice and research,” facilitating collaboration during implementation.

4. **Dissemination and valorisation phase:** The dissemination and valorisation phase includes networking activities that enhance the visibility of research outcomes and promote their application in clinical settings. This phase was primarily associated with barriers related to ‘incentive structures’ and the ‘alignment between research outputs and clinical needs’.

One key theme emerged:

- **Impact of research:** Participants highlighted the importance of enabling healthcare professionals to “see the direct impact of their contributions, fostering a sense of value and motivation.” Living Labs were seen as a way for professionals to “be a part of the improvement of the system,” reinforcing a sense of ownership and practical relevance.

Discussion

This study presents early findings toward the development of a framework that supports the integration of Living Labs into clinical environments to overcome key barriers to externally initiated research. Among the identified challenges, ‘time constraints’ and ‘care-flow priorities’ emerged as the most pressing, followed by the ‘misalignment between research agendas and clinical needs’, and inadequate ‘incentive structures’.

The structure of the proposed framework aligns with the research process phases outlined in the Living Lab Management System developed by the VITALISE project and the ENoLL Harmonization Working Group (Konstantinidis et al., 2024). These phases

broadly correspond to those described in the IDEAL framework (Idea, Development, Exploration, Assessment, and Long-Term Monitoring)(Hirst et al., 2013), which has been widely adopted in surgical research and beyond (Khachane et al., 2018). In our adaptation, the Exploration and Assessment phases are consolidated into a single Implementation phase to better reflect the practical realities and time constraints of clinical settings. Additionally, the framework can be further aligned with models that emphasize patient engagement in research, such as the work of Ruco and Nichol (2016) (Ruco & Nichol, 2016), thus reinforcing Living Labs' dual role in engaging both professionals and end-users.

Our findings suggest that Living Labs can function as hubs for real-world experimentation, embedded in routine clinical care. By leveraging well-established participatory methods such as co-creation and co-production, Living Labs create opportunities for professionals to become active participants in research. This fosters a sense of co-ownership and increases the relevance of research outcomes to everyday practice. Furthermore, Living Labs offer mechanisms for academic recognition (e.g., co-authorship, certificates) and continuous professional development (e.g., mentoring, skills-building), which can serve as effective incentives for clinician involvement.

Importantly, to address time-related constraints, the prioritization of research projects must be led by clinical professionals, with Living Labs acting as facilitators in aligning research efforts with real-world clinical needs. Moreover, systematic impact assessment and valorisation of results within the clinical setting are essential to ensure that research translates into tangible improvements in care.

Conclusion

This research-in-progress outlines an initial framework for integrating Living Labs into clinical research settings to address persistent barriers faced by healthcare professionals. By mapping challenges and solutions across key research phases, the framework highlights the potential of Living Labs to facilitate co-created, relevant, and implementable research. As next steps, we aim to expand the number of respondents to strengthen the validity of our findings. Following this, we will organize a stakeholder workshop to align outcomes and refine the framework collaboratively. Once the initial version is established, a Delphi study will be conducted to validate and consolidate expert consensus on the framework's components.

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